

conformal boundary $z \rightarrow 0$

$g_{\text{III}} \rightarrow 0$ (bulk leg pinches off)

$K(T, \Pi) \rightarrow \infty$ (curvature diverges)

$z = O(1)$:

finitely curved interior

thermal--bulk sector of the massive moment manifold